

GEODETIC PROVISION AS A TOOL OF RESISTANT DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

Geodetic provision is a means of sustainable development of modern society and the use of space according to the interest of human society and its appropriation. The geodetic provision is connected with regional economy, territorial analysis and sustainable development.

Keywords: geodetic provision, analytical-measurement functions, prospective analysis, retrospective analysis, optimization.

Geodetic provision (GP) has multi-aspect functions. In essence, they are servile and are performed by various departments, organizations, departments, groups of specialists. The forms and directions of GP in modern society are related to science, construction, design, operation of facilities, modernization, improvement, economics, Cadastre and many other various scientific and experimental fields of activity [1].

There are three main forms of timeline presentation: linear, cyclogram, and grid, including generalized models. It should be noted that traditional network models have a number of disadvantages associated with the complexity of presenting the organization of construction flows, a flexible connection of individual flows. Generalized network models combine the advantages of linear models in modeling work and the advantages of traditional network models in terms of operational management of the construction process.

The characteristics of different types of GP depend on the sphere of their application. And these spheres can be different depending on the requirements, structure, accuracy, calculation of the GP.

The GP complex has many features of the system. That is, GP as a complex consists of planned and multi-storey coordinates of various levels interacting with each other due to their accuracy and purpose, some common technologies and means of measurement, methods for improving measurement results, etc. consists of.

Within the framework of one post, it is impossible to cover all forms and directions of GP, since the spectrum of use of GP is very wide. We will rather touch on those directions of the Geodetic support complex that have been little studied or not explored at all to date.

There are various tasks of Geodetic provision [2]. It is not an abstract technology, but rather focuses on the exploration and support of a specific object of study. Geodetic support can be considered not only instrumental technology. Its composition includes measurement, measurement processing, their comprehensive analysis. The table below provides analytical and measurement functions of Geodetic support (tab.1).

Table 1.

Analytical-measurement functions

Measurement, processing	A retrospective analysis
Perspective analysis	Optimization

Apparently, not a specific function is presented here, but a group of functions. In the sequence of technological support, a group of measurement functions always comes first, which includes measurement processing. Measurements carried out regularly and over a long period of time provide a basis for conducting a retrospective analysis. This is the second analytical function of retrospective analysis. The function of retrospective analysis allows us to reveal the traditions that currently exist. The third analytical function of Geodetic provision is the function of prospective analysis or forecasting. As a rule, based on the analysis, several options or alternatives for the development of the object of study are identified. Therefore, the last group of functions is a group of functions that optimize decision - making and alternative options.

Result

It can be concluded that Geodetic provision in a broad sense is a means of sustainable development of society, the development and assimilation of space in the interests of human society, which connects Geodetic provision with the regional economy, analysis and sustainable development of the territory.

Literature

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